

Speculation on the Special Relativistic Transformation of Heat

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In (1) it is suggested that heat transforms as $1/g$ rest energy and not as $g \cdot$ rest energy, like a usual rest mass, where $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. This conclusion follows from applying $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ where $p = m_0 g v$ for a constant v , but changing m_0 . Furthermore, the relationship: $\text{delta energy} = \text{delta } q + \text{Work}$ is applied where $\text{delta } q$ is heat.

We suggest that the problem as introduced in (1), which is apparently representative of a set of work in the literature as stated in (1), is really concerned with the addition of a piece of mass m_1 at rest to a mass M moving at constant velocity v along the x direction. If one were to accelerate m_1 (rest mass) to the speed of v in the x -direction and then add it to M , the work $W = \text{Integral delta } (m_1 g)$ would be done to m_1 for v_1 (velocity) going from 0 to v . There would be no work involved adding an m_1 rest mass moving at v along x to M . Thus, overall work would equal the change in energy, unlike the result of (1). This suggests that heat transforms as any other kind of rest mass. Furthermore, we argue that one need not worry whether m_1 is of the form of a heat or not and so does not need to use the first law of thermodynamics a priori.

Argument of (1)

In (1), the first law of thermodynamics is assumed a priori:

$\text{Delta energy} = \text{delta } Q + W$, where Q is heat and W work ((1))

In the rest frame, if one adds heat to a gas at rest, its rest mass increases by the amount $\text{delta } Q$, but one might just as well have added more gas particles at the same temperature to increase the rest mass by the same amount, we argue. In other words, we suggest that one does not need to know the details of the rest mass. Even if one deals with heat, it is not clear that one needs ((1)) if this heat term can be described abstractly as extra rest mass. Nevertheless, we keep ((1)) to demonstrate the argument of (1).

Next, (1) considers: $\text{Integral } dp = \text{Integral } F dt$ ((2)) (p =momentum, F force)

Here $\text{Integral } dp = (M+m_1) gv - Mgv$ and $\text{Integral } Fdt = 1/v \text{ Work}$ if v =constant ((3))

M is moving with constant speed in the x direction and m_1 is at rest. We note that if m_1 were moving at a speed of v along the x direction, there would be no work done. Thus, v is not a constant from the point of view of m_1 . Nevertheless, we retain ((3)) in order to reproduce the argument of (1).

$g \text{ delta rest mass} = W/(vv)$ and from ((1)) $g \text{ delta rest mass} = Q + W$ so: $Q = W/(vv) \cdot (1/(gg))$ ((4)) or

$Q = (\text{delta rest mass}) (1/g)$ ((5))

Note: There seems to be a typo in (1) which indicates that $Q = (\Delta \text{rest mass}) / (gg)$

We note that the result ((5)) is apparently indicative of a number of works in the literature as noted in (1).

Alternative Approach

We speculate on an alternative approach which yields a different result for the transformation of heat. As noted, if one accelerates a rest mass, m_1 , from $v=0$ to v in the x direction, then:

$$\Delta \text{energy} = m_1 g - m_1 = \text{Work} \quad ((6))$$

We suggest that if one adds rest mass, one does not need to know the details of this rest mass. It could be heat, potential energy or usual rest mass etc. As a result, we suggest that ((1)) is not required. One may solve the problem for an abstract rest mass addition, and then argue at the end that it is equivalent to heat. Physically, it is known that one may create exothermic reactions at any point in time and create heat. Thus, one need not deal with heat at the offset, we argue.

If one accelerates m_1 to the speed v and then adds it to M , one essentially has the changed system described in (1). Originally, one had: m_1 at rest and M (rest mass) moving at v and later one has $(M+m_1)$ rest mass moving at v . In the description above:

$$\text{Change in energy} = m_1 g - m_1 = W \quad ((7))$$

To see this explicitly, consider: $\int dp = \int m_0 v dv / (1 - v^2/c^2)^{1.5} = \int F v dt = \text{Work}$

$$\text{Work} = \int m_0 dv v / (1 - v^2/c^2)^{1.5} = \int d(mog) \quad ((8))$$

((7)) suggests that Q (heat) transforms as regular rest mass energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that the problem of adding a piece of rest mass m_1 at rest to a rest mass M moving at constant velocity v along the x axis, is the same as accelerating m_1 from $v=0$ to v and then adding it to the moving M . In such a case, $\text{Work} = m_1 g - m_1$. Thus, overall change in energy is equal to work. One may then suggest that m_1 is really heat energy. In other words, we suggest that one need not know the details of the rest mass, be it usual rest mass, potential energy or heat energy. This implies that one does not need to use the first law of thermodynamics a priori.

This also suggests that heat energy transforms as usual rest mass energy under a Lorentz transformation.

References

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